

Article

A Review of Blockchain Technology Adoption in the Tourism Industry from a Sustainability Perspective

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Abstract: The deployment of Blockchain technology in the tourism industry is already becoming a reality with the gradual emergence of innovative business models. At its core is the promise of improving the efficiency of the tourism service value chain and enhancing the quality of the service provided to the end customer. This paper analyses research trends focused on using Blockchain technology in tourism. The aim is to determine how this technology impacts the tourism sector and its sustainability. A systematic review, descriptive bibliometric analysis, and network analysis based on co-authorship, co-citation, and keyword analysis criteria, among others, have been used. The results reveal that the subject matter analysed is generating a growing trend in academic research in the fields of sustainable management and supply chain efficiency. The activities in the tourism sector that are incorporating this technology to a greater extent are those related to the areas of marketing, logistics, and smart business models, according to the data extracted from the analysis. This technology already enables the application of solutions that predict and promote tourist behaviour based on sustainable behaviour and consumption habits, generating value for the different stakeholders.

Keywords: blockchain; tourism; sustainability; bibliometrics analysis; cost efficiency; tourist behaviour; traceability

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1. Introduction

The Blockchain is a decentralised distributed ledger that operates using a consensus protocol and an appendix-like data structure that, due to its architecture, is resistant to modification. The main characteristic of this technology is that the blocks of data generated by this technology are capable of storing a system and the service that this system provides. Each transaction stores data such as sender, receiver, time, asset type, and asset quantity. This type of service can consist of simply transferring some crypto-token or the execution of a Smart Contract [1], for example, the automatic resolution of a tourist accommodation rental contract if a series of instructions given to the system are fulfilled [2].

This paper aims to carry out a systematic review of the academic literature associated with Blockchain technology applied to the tourism sector and its sustainability by searching the Web of Science (WoS) database. In addition, in the second part, a biometric analysis is also carried out, which is very useful when assessing the dissemination of the academic literature in the investigated area. Blockchain technology is generating much academic literature in recent years [3]. Still, it has yet to be analysed from the perspective of improving processes in the tourism sector, especially in those processes that affect the impact of tourism activities on the sustainability of the industry itself and the different stakeholders involved [4]. This analysis aims to reveal how research in the above fields is evolving to the present day, information that can be crucial to identify potential research areas.

The primary beneficiaries of this work will be researchers who can use the knowledge generated as a research trend and other collectives that intend to invest in projects based

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